

AN EXPERIMENTAL AND COMPUTATIONAL INVESTIGATION OF CHIRAL RECOGNITION IN SOLUTION

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Chiral molecules are non-superimposable mirror images of each other. Enantiomers are the most prominent class of these compounds, which have gained attention for their applications in pharmaceutical, agricultural, and food industries. They may form distinct interactions with other chiral molecules, resulting in different chemical and biological activities. Therefore, the structural identification of each isomer is critical and remains a challenge for experiment and theory fields.[1] Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) with Matrix-Assisted Diffusion-Ordered Spectroscopy is an emerging approach that utilizes a chiral matrix to investigate enantiomeric mixtures. Basically, the medium is modified with the addition of chiral matrix compounds that interact differently with each enantiomer of the mixture, allowing the differentiation and chiral assignment.[2] However, this method lacks detailed insights into the chiral recognition modes and the complexation process at the molecular level. Therefore, in this study, we integrate experimental investigations with computational methods to explore the chiral-selective interactions responsible for the discrimination of mandelic acid (MA) enantiomers with (*R* and *S*)-BINOL as a chiral matrix in solution.

For this purpose, ¹H and diffusion NMR measurements in CDCl₃ were conducted on a 600 MHz spectrometer. Additionally, DFT and molecular dynamics (MD) studies were performed to support the experimental findings. The experimental results reveal that the MA enantiomer exhibiting the highest shielding effect shares the same chirality as the employed BINOL. On the opposite, the enantiomer interacting more strongly (lower diffusion coefficient) has the opposite stereochemistry to the BINOL. DFT studies at the PW6B95/def2-TZVPD level confirm the preferred formation of enantioselective binding and emphasize the role of intermolecular hydrogen bonding to explain the observed shielding effects. MD simulations provide dynamic properties, such as diffusion coefficients, in good agreement with the experimental data. Furthermore, classical simulations offer valuable insights into the complexation process between MA and BINOL over time, enhancing our understanding of experimental observations. The MD results also indicate a higher local concentration of (*R*)-BINOL molecules surrounding the (*S*)-MA compared to (*R*)-MA, explaining the lower diffusion coefficient observed for (*S*)-MA; and the opposite trend for (*S*)-BINOL. Hence, this integrated approach illustrates the feasibility of enantio-selective discrimination as a combination of NMR and theoretical studies to unravel chiral recognition.

[1] M. S. Silva, *Molecules*, 22 (2017) 247.

[2] K. S. Salome, C. F. Tormena, *Chem. Comm.*, 59 (2019), 8611.